

Influence of Negative Sequence Injection Strategies on Faulted Phase Selector Performance

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Abstract: Renewable power is expected to increase drastically in the coming years due to the energy transition. A large part of the newly installed generators will be connected to the power electronics system through inverters and electronic converters, whose behaviour differs from the generators connected synchronously to the network. One of the main differences is the current contribution during symmetrical and asymmetrical faults which can affect protection systems. New grid codes establish requirements for fast current injection, but the converters maximum current limitations during faults make it difficult to establish control strategies for such current contribution. This paper studies the influence of current injection strategies on the performance of faulted phase selector algorithm of a commercial relay. Two positive and negative sequence current injection strategies in compliance with new Spanish grid code requirements have been proposed and tested under fault conditions in HiL (Hardware In the Loop). Test results show that the selected injection strategy affects the fault phase identification algorithm. Furthermore, the negative sequence injection requirements established in the new grid code improve the relay performance when line-to-line faults are applied, but they are not enough to identify all fault types.

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1. Introduction

The energy transition challenge needs to increase renewable generation penetration level, displacing conventional synchronous generation. Many of these renewable generators are based on power electronics whose behaviour differs from the conventional generator in normal operation and during events. In the case of faults in the electric power system, the difference between the current contributions can affect the protection system behaviour endangering system stability [1]. In addition to a lower value in the current supply during the fault, that can affect detection and selectivity problems [2] [3], many renewable generators based on power electronic provide a balanced current in both balanced and unbalanced faults.

On the other hand, during faults in the electric power system, the power park modules (PPM) must help overcome the voltage dip by supplying reactive current as established in the network grid codes [4]. In balanced faults, PPMs provide a balanced reactive current, then the voltage in all phases will increase in the same way, but, in the case of unbalanced faults, a balanced current supply can produce overvoltage in the healthy phases, affecting the safety of the system [5]. Moreover, the algorithms implemented in the protection relays require a minimum active positive sequence current for proper

functioning. Therefore, it is necessary to supply positive and negative sequence reactive current, that is, unbalanced reactive current, and active current in positive sequence during unbalanced faults.

Fast current injection requirements are established in the different grid codes to regulate the current contribution during balanced and unbalanced faults. In Europe, the European directive [6] allows network operators in coordination with transmission system operators (TSO) of each zone to define the requirements of fast fault current injection before asymmetrical faults. For example, the Spanish transmission system operator (REE), specifies in the PO 12.2 operating procedure [7] the requirements for negative sequence current injection, the same as the German [8] [9] or Greece [10] Generally, all these grid codes state that the increment of reactive current in the positive and negative sequences is proportional to the depth of the voltage dip.

Some studies have been performed regarding negative sequence contribution. [11] investigates the reduction of unbalanced voltage when negative sequence current injection is carried out. This paper proposes and analyses several injection strategies from voltage support point of view but does not analyze the influence of these strategies in the behavior of protection relay algorithms.[12] studies the interaction between negative sequence injection provided by PV plants and the directional elements of transmission line relays.[13] studies the influence of inverter-based resources control in several protection functions of the relay (50Q, 51Q and 67Q) comparing negative sequence impedance. It shows the malfunction of 51Q and 67Q through simulation examples run in electromagnetic transient programs (EMTP) but it only uses Hardware in the Loop (HiL) to test 67Q. Although this paper also explains that faulted phase identification (FID) may be influenced by the impact of the WG phase angle of the negative sequence current, the analysis is only carried out by EMT simulations.

This paper aims to study and test the effect of fast fault current injection strategies in the FID from commercial relays typically used in the distribution grid. To carry out this task, initially, two strategies compliant with the Spanish grid code are proposed and implemented in the power electronic interfaces used by PV and Type-IV wind turbines RSCAD models. Once the strategies are modelled, HiL is used to check their impact in FID of a commercial relay.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the fault phase selector algorithm implemented in the commercial relay to test during this study. Section 3 summarizes the grid code requirements regarding low voltage ride through and fast fault current injection. Section 4 propose fast fault current injection strategies proposed to fulfil grid code requirements and after that, in section 5 it is described the general control block diagram implemented in the power electronic interfaces model used by PV and Type-IV wind turbines to fulfil grid code requirements. The laboratory test bench used to evaluate the new strategies in relay behaviour is described in section 6. Finally, the main results and conclusions of the study are included in section 7 and 8.

2. Faulted phase selector algorithm

The main function of faulted phase selectors is to identify both the type of fault and the phases involved. Once this identification is performed, the results are provided to the different protection algorithms whose operation depends on this information, for example, the release of impedance loops of a distance function or directional elements.

The faulted phase selection algorithms of the overcurrent commercial relay have been tested in this study. This algorithm, which is based on sequence-current theory, is shown in Figure 1. This figure shows the angular relationship between the negative current (I_2) and the pure positive sequence current (I_{1f}) used by the commercial relay to identify asymmetrical faults. Figure 1 a) is used to identify single-phase or two-phase to ground faults, and Figure 1 b) to identify two-phase faults.

Figure 1. a) Two-Phase fault angle diagram; b) Single phase and two phase to ground fault angle diagram [14].

3. European grid code requirements review. Spanish example

All generators must meet the requirements established by the TSO of the network to which they are connected. These requirements depend on the generator installed power and/or the voltage of the point of connection. [15] classifies power generation modules into Type A, Type B, Type C and Type D with different power and voltage ranges. In the Spanish Grid Code [15], power generation modules that have installed electric power in the range of 100 kW to 5 MW are considered as Type B modules and 5 MW to 50MW as Type C modules. This paper is focused on distributed generation, so only requirements for Type B and Type C have been considered.

When there is a fault in the electric grid, the PV and Type-IV wind turbine generation must remain connected to the grid for a minimum time to ensure the power system operation is secure and reliable. This operational behaviour is known as *Low Voltage Ride Through (LVRT)* [16]. Figure 2 shows the Spanish grid code profile for LVRT that must be satisfied by Type B and Type C generation modules. It shows the relationship between the voltage dip depth (ΔU in p.u.) measured in the connection point (P_{cc}) and the minimum time for the electrical power module to remain connected.

Figure 2. Low voltage ride through applied to type B and type C electric power plant module [7].

Besides, before a voltage dip, the reactive current injected must increase depending on the voltage depth. The new grid code published in July 2020 [15] established the necessity of negative sequence current injection for Type B and Type C generators when an unsymmetrical fault is applied. The reactive current injection must be according to the profiles shown in the following figure.

Figure 3. a) Injection/consumption of additional positive reactive current (ΔI_{1r}) depending on positive voltage drop, b) Total reactive current Injection/Consumption limitation (I_r), c) Injection/consumption of additional negative reactive current (ΔI_{2r}) depending on negative voltage drop [7].

Where ΔU_1 represents the voltage drop/rise in the positive sequence, ΔU_2 represents the voltage/rise drop in the negative sequence, and K_1 and K_2 are proportional constants in the positive and negative sequence. These constant values vary in the range 2-6, as is shown in Figure 3.

From Figure 3, it is concluded that under unbalanced faults, the control of the electric power module injects a positive and negative sequence reactive current proportional to the voltage deep by a factor K . Furthermore, the figure shows the maximum current provided by the control of the power converter.

The following figure shows the contribution of a synchronous generator to a two-phase AB fault. During the fault, for 30% depth voltage dip (V^+ and V^-), the generator supplies reactive currents in positive ($I_r(+)$) and negative ($I_r(-)$) sequence proportional to the voltage dip ($K_1=2.8$ and $K_2=2$), as indicated in the network code. This synchronous generator injects a phase current that reaches 2.2 p.u. in phase A and 1.8 p.u. in phase B. This behaviour is not possible in a power electronics-based generator due to the current limitations imposed by the converter. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze how this type of generators can supply negative sequence current during unbalanced faults without exceeding the power converter limits. With this objective, the next section proposes different strategies for active and reactive current injection under unbalanced faults. After, the general control diagram implemented in the power electronic interfaces model used by PV and Type-IV wind turbines is described.

Figure 4. a) Positive (V+) and negative voltage (V-), b) Phase current injection, c) Active (Ia+) and reactive (Ir+) current in positive sequence, c) Active (Ia-) and reactive (Ir-) current in negative sequence.

4. Current fault injection before unsymmetrical faults by power electronic-based generator

The traditional protection schemes are designed based on the current contribution of the conventional synchronous generator under fault conditions, but the behaviour of power electronic-based generators differs during faults. As explained in section 3, conventional synchronous generators can provide currents several times greater than nominal current during unbalanced faults. In contrast, current in power electronic-based generators is limited to avoid exceeding their designed current ratings. Therefore, it is not always possible to provide the reactive current in positive and negative sequence and the active current in the positive sequence from the direct application of the Figure 3 without exceeding the limits of the power inverter, and it is necessary to establish a system of priorities so as not to exceed the current ratings of the converters.

After analyzing the grid code summarised in section 3 [15], two strategies (strategy A and B) have been proposed. These strategies establish the priority of positive and negative sequence current injection before unbalanced faults considering the limits of the power converter and considering the same K factor for positive and negative sequence based on synchronous generator behaviour.

Figure 5 shows the flowchart from strategy A. If an unbalanced fault is applied, this strategy prioritizes the active and reactive current injection in the positive sequence over the negative sequence reactive current injection. In the first step, active and reactive current in the positive sequence is calculated based on Figure 3 a) and compared with the

maximum phase current limit ($I_{max,phase}$). If such limit is not reached, the negative sequence reactive current is calculated according to Figure 3 c) considering the same K -factor ($K_1 = K_2$). Still, if the value obtained exceeds the maximum current, K_2 is reduced until the said limit is fulfilled. Moreover, it must be considered that a minimum negative sequence reactive current injection is not defined in this strategy.

Figure 5. Strategy A flowchart to fulfill fast fault current injection requirement

In strategy B, described in Figure 6, the power converter control prioritizes the positive and negative sequence reactive current injection over the positive sequence active current injection during unbalanced faults. The same K -factors between 2 and 6 are initially selected to calculate the reactive current injection ($K_1 = K_2$) in the first step. Still, they will be reduced at the same proportion during the fault to fulfil maximum reactive current injection limitation (I_{LimU}), which is lower than the maximum total current ($I_{max,phase}$). The active current injection in the positive sequence is calculated considering the margin between the maximum current ($I_{max,phase}$) and the maximum reactive current injection (I_{LimU}).

Figure 6. Strategy B flowchart to fulfill fast fault current injection requirement.

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5. Control diagram of power electronic interfaces devices to be used during the study

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The strategies proposed in the previous section are modelled in the outer control loop of a PV and a Type-IV wind turbine power converters whose structure is shown in Figure 7. The controls technique used by the power converters is based on the decoupling control structure in a d-q reference framework that permits managing active and reactive power, independently [17], [18]. The following figure shows a schematic diagram of the implemented control.

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Figure 7. Schematic control diagram.

As shown in Figure 7, under normal conditions the active current loop controls the DC bus voltage of the power converter and the active power delivered by the generator. Moreover, the reactive current control manages the voltage at the converter connection point or fixes the reactive power provided to the grid.

During fault conditions, the reactive current control must provide voltage support based on the grid code requirements, considering the maximum current supplied by the converter to avoid undesirable damage to the equipment.

To carry out these tasks, initially, the three-phase voltages (V_{abc}) and current waveforms (I_{abc}) are measured at the common coupling point (PCC). These time-domain waveforms are initially decomposed in stationary frame α - β using power variant Clarke transform [19] [20]. After the decomposition, voltage and current values are split in positive and negative sequence. From the decomposition and using Park transformation [20], [21], d-q parameters in both sequences are obtained ($V_{dq(+)}$, $V_{dq(-)}$, $I_{dq(+)}$, $I_{dq(-)}$). These d-q values are used by the control in steady state conditions and under fault conditions.

In normal conditions, current and voltages in negative sequence are close to zero. Therefore, negative sequence control loop is deactivated, and only positive sequence control operates. By contrast, in unbalanced faults, according to grid code requirements described in section 3, the power converter must supply positive and negative sequence current and so, positive and negative control loops are activated.

Based on the control diagram described, and considering the strategies previously detailed, the following scheme is introduced in the control diagram (Figure 7) during $I_{d, fault}$ and $I_{q, fault}$ calculation in positive and negative sequences under fault conditions:

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Figure 8. Control methodology to inject positive and negative sequence current.

To analyze the influence of these strategies on faulted phase selector algorithm operation described in section 4, several tests has been carried out in the laboratory test bench described in the next section.

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6. Laboratory test bench

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The two strategies proposed are tested in the benchmark grid model shown in Figure 9. In this benchmark grid, the external grid is represented by a Thevenin equivalent, and it is connected to the distribution level by a 55/12 kV transformer. The MV side grounding of such transformer is set to consider a grounded and an ungrounded distribution grid topology in the analysis. A 11 MW renewable generator is connected at the point indicated as “RES” in the figures. In the tests, two technologies are considered: PV and a Type-IV wind turbine. Overhead lines are used to connect renewable technologies to the distribution grid, and the lightning symbol represents the fault inception point. The following fault types have been applied at this point:

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- Single line to ground faults (SLG): AG, BG and CG

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- Line to line faults (LL): AB, BC, CA

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- Line to line to ground faults (LLG): ABG, BCG and CAG

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Figure 9. Benchmark distribution grid used to analyze relay performance.

The analysis of commercial protection systems is performed by Hardware in the Loop (HiL) configuration with a RTDS simulator. Figure 10 shows the scheme used during the study.

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RTDS is a real-time digital simulator that reproduces events that can appear in the electric grid, generates current and voltages seen by the relay during a fault, and records the relay behavior under this scenario.

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The benchmark distribution grid is modelled in RSCAD software to perform the study and simulate it by the RTDS, which generates the current and voltage values to be measured by relay. These values are in the range ± 10 V, so that the amplifier amplifies them to represent the actual secondary values measured by the relay. The amplifier has six current and voltage channels with a maximum output voltage and current values of

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300 V_{rms} and 70 A_{rms}. Once the current and voltage values are amplified, they are used to supply the voltages and currents analogic inputs of the relay that produce a trip signal when a fault current is detected and send this signal to the RTDS to continue the simulation.

Figure 10. Hardware in the loop configuration.

7. Results and discussion

Table 1 summarizes the results obtained in the tests described in the previous section when the renewable source is a PV generator. These results show that both strategies improve faulted phase detection in LL faults with respect to the behaviour of the algorithm when only a positive sequence current is supplied. Nevertheless, they still cannot correctly identify LLG faults.

Regarding SLG faults, two situations can be distinguished in the table. In ungrounded systems, these faults cannot be detected using phase overcurrent protection. This fact is indicated in the table as NA (Not Applicable). In the grounded distribution system, the faulted phase selector results before SLG faults depend on the current injection strategy, identifying it correctly with Strategy A but not with Strategy B.

In LL faults, the phase selection is subjected to the initial *K*-factor with Strategy A; for example, it fails if *K*-factor is 3.5 but detects correctly if this parameter is set to 2.5. However, Strategy B uses a calculated *K*-factor that considers the current limit of the converter for the other fault types, but the behaviour is still wrong for this fault type.

Table 1. Study cases to evaluate negative current injection in current protection relays located in distribution grids ($K_1=K_2$)

Fault type	PV (Strategy A)		PV (Strategy B)	
	Ungrounded	Grounded	Ungrounded	Grounded
AG		✓		✗
BG	N.A.	✓	N.A.	✗
CG		✓		✗
AB	✓	~	✓	✓
BC	✓	~	✓	✓
CA	✓	~	✓	✓
ABG	✗	✗	✗	✗

BCG	x	x	x	x
CAG	x	x	x	x

Furthermore, to observe the influence of the initial K -factor value in test results, the AB fault in the grounded system is analyzed when the initial K -factor is set to 2.5 or 3.5. In these conditions, when strategy A is used, faulted phase selector operation depends on such initial K -factor, as shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12. If the K -factor is set to 2.5 (Figure 11), the relay can identify the AB fault correctly, but the faulted phase selector algorithm identifies a three-phase fault when 3.5 is used (Figure 12). By contrast, Strategy B provides the same faulted phase identification for both initial K -factor values. Therefore, Strategy A is more sensitive to the initial K -factor than Strategy B because faulted phase selector operation changes depending on such value. Thus, strategy B is the most stable because the result does not depend on the initial settings, but K -factor during the fault is out of the range defined in the grid codes.

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Figure 11. Faulted phase selector when AB fault is applied and K -factor=2.5 using Strategy A

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Figure 12. Faulted phase selector when AB fault is applied and K -factor=3.5 using Strategy A.

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Figure 13. Faulted phase selector when AB fault is applied and K -factor=2.5 using Strategy B.

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Figure 14. Faulted phase selector when AB fault is applied and K -factor=3.5 using Strategy B.

Moreover, the maximum current limit of the power converter can make the K -factor fall below the minimum indicated in the grid code when Strategy B is used. When an unbalanced fault is applied in this strategy, the reactive current increments in positive and negative sequences are calculated depending on the voltage dip depth and the initial K -factor value selected. Nevertheless, these reactive current values may exceed the imposed limit of 0.9 p.u. In these conditions, initial K_1 and K_2 factors are reduced in the same proportion to satisfy the required limit for reactive current values. This effect is shown in Figure 15 for a PV generator before an AB fault in the undergrounded system. In the example, the initial K -factor value is 2.5. When the fault is applied, the reactive current changes depending on the dip depth shown in Figure 15 a), but the calculated current is above the maximum limit, activating the limitation flag (Figure 15 c). This flag indicates that the K -factor must be reduced to avoid converter damage and satisfy the reactive current injection requirement.

Figure 15. K-factor when AB fault is applied and PV plant is connected

This strategy has been tested in the benchmark described in section 6, obtaining the results shown in Table 2, which summarizes the K -factor average value obtained in the simulations. In all these simulations, the reactive current before the event is 0.129 p.u., the initial K -factor value is 2.5, and the fault has been produced at 50% of the line shown in Figure 9. In each case, the depth of the voltage dip depends on the fault type; for example, in the AB fault simulated in the grounded configuration, the voltage dip depth is 0.42 p.u., and for AG fault 0.2 p.u. The highest values of K -factor are obtained for SLG faults, but they are still below the 2.0 limit from the requirements even so the low value for voltage dip depth. This scenario is not considered in the network code, but it is in the NTS [22] that is used to verify the compliance of the generation unit. It indicates that if the factors are less than indicated, it will be considered valid if the positive and negative sequence components are limited to the same proportion or that the positive sequence component will be higher than 40% of the apparent nominal current. In this case, the first condition is met.

Table 2. K -factor values when strategy B is applied for negative current injection.

Fault type	PV		Type-IV wind turbine	
	Ungrounded	Grounded	Ungrounded	Grounded
AG	N.A.	1.460	N.A.	1.937
BG		1.350		1.966

CG		1.420		1.947
AB	0.920	1.055	1.299	1.361
BC	0.885	1.038	1.307	1.361
CA	0.975	1.111	1.306	1.375
ABG	0.934	1.034	1.315	1.333
BCG	0.884	1.000	1.314	1.346
CAG	0.983	1.073	1.308	1.355
ABC	1.015	1.013	1.178	1.209

8. Conclusions

This paper analyzes the performance of the faulted phase selector of a commercial overcurrent relay before different injection strategies in compliance with new Spanish grid code requirements.

Two positive and negative sequence current injection strategies have been defined considering such requirements and the limitations imposed by power converters from renewable generators. To check the influence of these strategies in commercial relays, they are implemented and tested by HiL. In these tests, a real-time digital simulator reproduces events in a benchmark grid, generates current and voltages measured by the commercial relay during a fault, and records the relay behaviour under these scenarios.

From test results is concluded that the behaviour of the faulted phase selector depends on the current injection strategy. Both strategies ameliorate the phase identification regarding the strategies that only inject positive sequence current even under unbalanced faults, but it is not enough to correctly identify faulted phase in every unbalanced fault type. In fact, line to line to ground faults are not correctly identified in any test performed. Consequently, new fault phase selector algorithms are still needed to guarantee the correct faulted phase identification and ensure the reliability of the protection installed and, consequently, the stability of the electric power system.

On the other hand, another conclusion is related to the effect of the current injection defined in the grid code. Comparing the proposed strategies, phase selection with Strategy B, which prioritizes the positive and negative current injection, is less sensitive to the initial K-factor value selected. Furthermore, it is seen that the obtained K-factor obtained by the algorithms depends on the injection strategy, the fault type, the fault deep and the maximum current injection from the power converter during faults. From tests, it is observed that the initial K-factor is reduced during unbalanced faults, even going outside the range defined.

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